

Relationship between Beta and Gamma functions

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Abstract. The article deals with a more in-depth study of one of the most interesting topics of mathematical analysis "Integrals beta and gamma".

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INTRODUCTION

The gamma function is said to be some extension of the factorial. Recall that the factorial operation was introduced for positive integers very simply $n! = 1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot \dots \cdot (n - 1) \cdot n$.

EULER INTEGRALS

If we now want to graph the factorial, we will get such a discrete set of points and the question arises: is it possible to extend this function to get intermediate values? Let's look at the basic property of the factorial $n! = n \cdot (n - 1)$ and the question arises whether there exists such a function which has the same property not only for integers, but for all integers in general.

Traditionally gamma and beta functions are associated with the name of Leonardo Euler and they are often called Euler integrals, perhaps Euler was originally looking for a function possessing the factorial property when he came up with the gamma function. But if its only application was limited to this continuation of the factorial, it would hardly have survived 3 centuries of much more important and interesting application of these functions related to their integral properties and the purpose of this article will be to obtain the basic properties and relations for these two functions that will allow you to immediately apply them and just abstractly reason about some fractional factorial. And let's start considering the function beta function is a function from two variables

$$B(a, b) = \int_0^1 t^{a-1} \cdot (1-t)^{b-1} dt$$

Generally in this beta and gamma functions are defined for complex numbers, but we will consider here only at real value. If here a and b are greater than one, it is a definite integral, and if less than one, it is not a proper integral and it will converge if $a > 0$ and $b > 0$ and only at such values this integral will define the beta function. And now let's get another representation for the beta function for this in the integral let's substitute $\sqrt{t} = \sin\varphi$, which will be with the limits of integration $t = 0 \Rightarrow \varphi = 0$ и $t = 1 \Rightarrow \varphi = \frac{\pi}{2}$. It's clear that $t = \sin^2\varphi \Rightarrow 1-t = 1 - \sin^2\varphi = \cos^2\varphi$. I just need to find the differential $dt = 2\sin\varphi\cos\varphi d\varphi$ and substituting into the integral

$$\begin{aligned} B(a, b) &= \int_0^1 t^{a-1} \cdot (1-t)^{b-1} dt = \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} (\sin^2\varphi)^{a-1} (\cos^2\varphi)^{b-1} \cdot 2\sin\varphi\cos\varphi d\varphi = \\ &= \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} 2(\sin\varphi)^{2a-1} (\cos\varphi)^{2b-1} d\varphi. \end{aligned}$$

Thus we have obtained one more integral representation and about this function the first of them will allow us to find some types of integrals with roots and the second with open functions now let's find one value for example, it will be needed later. Let $a = \frac{1}{2}$ and $b = \frac{1}{2}$ Then $2a - 1 = 0$ and $2b - 1 = 0$. We substitute this into the integral and get:

$$B\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}\right) = \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} 2d\varphi = 2\varphi \Big|_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} = \pi.$$

GAMMA FUNCTION

Now let's deal with the gamma function. The gamma function is a function from one variable, let us denote it by the letter $\Gamma(a)$ and take the following function as a definition

$$\Gamma(a) = \int_0^{\infty} t^{a-1} \cdot e^{-t} dt$$

Although the gamma function can be defined for complex numbers we will consider here only at the real argument and this integral converges only at $a > 0$. And hence it only defines the gamma function when a is greater than zero. Now substitute instead of a , $a + 1$ then the gamma function

$$\Gamma(a + 1) = \int_0^{\infty} t^a \cdot e^{-t} dt$$

Let us apply to this integral the method of integration by parts over the function $u = t^a \Rightarrow du = a \cdot t^{a-1} dt$ for $dv = e^{-t} dt \Rightarrow v = -e^{-t}$. Now for the formula for integration by parts:

$$\Gamma(a + 1) = \int_0^{\infty} t^a \cdot e^{-t} dt = -t^a \cdot e^{-t} \Big|_0^{\infty} + a \int_0^{\infty} t^{a-1} \cdot e^{-t} dt.$$

Hence

$$\Gamma(a + 1) = a\Gamma(a).$$

And it turns out that the gamma function has the property of factorial, but not only for integers, but for any integers at all. Let's find what the gamma of one is equal to

$$\Gamma(1) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-t} dt = -e^{-t} \Big|_0^{\infty} = -\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} e^{-t} + 1 = 1.$$

Now let's use this recurrence relation

$$\Gamma(1) = 1$$

$$\Gamma(2) = 1 \cdot \Gamma(1) = 1$$

$$\Gamma(3) = 2 \cdot \Gamma(2) = 2 \cdot 1 = 2 = 2!$$

And thus to find all values of gamma function at integer positive arguments and the general formula can be written as

$$\Gamma(n + 1) = n!$$

Thus we have now proved the main property of the gamma function, which relates it to the factorial, and also found out that for positive integer arguments shifted by one. By the way, this displacement by one due to which we get here the displacement by one was introduced by Lezhandre and thanks to him these notations gamma and beta for the function we consider were spread. And although gamma and beta functions are most widespread in this form, this displacement annoys probably half of mathematicians. Gauss, for example, introduced a similar function without this bias, denoting it by the letter

$$\Pi(a) = \int_0^{\infty} t^a \cdot e^{-t} dt$$

and correspondingly at the whole argument n the value of this function

$$\Pi(n) = n!$$

and for example Riemann used exactly this pi function in his article on the zeta function, which was posed as a still unsolved million dollar problem let's see now what the graph of the function is.

Recall that the integral defines the gamma function only at $a > 0$, at $a = 0$ the integral diverges and the value of the gamma function tends to infinity. And we have already found that at integer values of the argument shifted by one the value of gamma function is equal to factorial. A little later we will get other known exact values for gamma function, but still most of its values are found only by approximate numerical methods. Generally they say it is enough to find the value of gamma function on some segment of unit length, for example from one to two, and then using this ratio we can find all other values. Although the integral defines the gamma function only at $a > 0$, we can consider that this relation holds for negative numbers as well. And thereby obtain the so-called analytic continuation for the gamma function to the area of negative values, that is, in the negative area because of this functional equation has much more applications than negative ones, so further we will consider only this area.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN BETA AND GAMMA FUNCTIONS

Now let us find the relationship between the gamma and beta function. First, we make the following substitution in the integral.

Let $t = \sqrt{x}$. Hence if at the lower limit $t = 0 \Rightarrow x = 0$, at the upper limit $t \rightarrow \infty \Rightarrow x \rightarrow \infty$. Let's express from here $t = x^2$, then the differential $dt = 2x dx$ and we'll get a replacement:

$$\Gamma(a) = \int_0^{\infty} t^{a-1} \cdot e^{-t} dt = \int_0^{\infty} (x^2)^{a-1} \cdot e^{-x^2} \cdot 2x dx = \int_0^{\infty} 2x^{2a-1} \cdot e^{-x^2} dx.$$

Thus, we have obtained one more integral representation for the gamma function and remember that we have previously obtained a representation for the beta function in the form of the following integral of trigonometric functions

$$B(a, b) = \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} 2 \cdot (\sin\varphi)^{2a-1} (\cos\varphi)^{2b-1} d\varphi$$

Let's write again the expression for the gamma function but with the argument b there will be a similar integral but as a variable of integration we will take not x but y it is clear that from this value of the integral cannot change.

$$\Gamma(b) = \int_0^{\infty} 2y^{2b-1} \cdot e^{-y^2} dy.$$

Now let's find the product of two gamma functions

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma(a) \cdot \Gamma(b) &= \int_0^{\infty} 2x^{2a-1} \cdot e^{-x^2} dx \cdot \int_0^{\infty} 2y^{2b-1} \cdot e^{-y^2} dy = \\ &= \iint_D 4x^{2a-1} \cdot y^{2b-1} \cdot e^{-x^2-y^2} dx dy \end{aligned}$$

Now in this integral we pass to polar coordinates for this purpose we make the following substitutions in the polar coordinate system

$$\begin{cases} x = r \cos \varphi & r \in [0, \infty) \\ y = r \sin \varphi & \varphi \in [0, \frac{\pi}{2}] \\ dx dy \rightarrow r dr d\varphi & \Rightarrow x^2 + y^2 = r^2 \Rightarrow e^{-x^2-y^2} = e^{-r^2} \end{cases}$$

As a result, after substitution the double integral will be equal to the repeated integral

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma(a) \cdot \Gamma(b) &= \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} d\varphi \int_0^{\infty} 4(r \cos \varphi)^{2a-1} (r \sin \varphi)^{2b-1} e^{-r^2} r dr = \\ &= \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} 2 \cdot (\cos \varphi)^{2a-1} (\sin \varphi)^{2b-1} d\varphi \int_0^{\infty} 2r^{2(a+b)-1} \cdot e^{-r^2} dr. \end{aligned}$$

Meaning,

$$\Gamma(a) \cdot \Gamma(b) = B(b, a) \cdot \Gamma(a + b)$$

Hence the beta function is equal to

$$B(b, a) = \frac{\Gamma(a) \cdot \Gamma(b)}{\Gamma(a + b)} = B(a, b)$$

Thus, we get such a beautiful formula linking the value of beta function and gamma function. This relation allows us to find the value of gamma function knowing the value of beta function and vice versa for an example we substitute this formula instead of a and b the number 1/2 and get:

$$\frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \cdot \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)}{\Gamma(1)} = B\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}\right) = \pi.$$

Hence we obtain

$$\Gamma^2\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = \pi \Rightarrow \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = \sqrt{\pi}.$$

Let's look at the integral defining the gamma function substituted for a 1/2, we get

$$\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = \int_0^{\infty} 2 \cdot e^{-x^2} dx = \sqrt{\pi}.$$

And from here we immediately obtain the value of the well-known integral, the so-called Euler-Poisson integral:

$$\int_0^{\infty} e^{-x^2} dx = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2}.$$

We know that the gamma from $\Gamma(a+1) = a\Gamma(a)$. Let's use this relation

$$\Gamma\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) = \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2} + 1\right) = \frac{1}{2}\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \sqrt{\pi}$$

$$\Gamma\left(\frac{5}{2}\right) = \frac{3}{2}\Gamma\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{3}{2} \cdot \sqrt{\pi}$$

The regularity is already clear we can continue this process to infinity and get the value for the gamma function for all positive semi-integer arguments and in general it can be written as

$$\Gamma\left(n + \frac{1}{2}\right) = \frac{1 \cdot 3 \cdot \dots \cdot (2n-1)}{2^n} \cdot \sqrt{\pi} = \frac{(2n-1)!!}{2^n} \cdot \sqrt{\pi} = \frac{(2n)!}{4^n \cdot n!} \sqrt{\pi}.$$

Thus, at this point we have found the value of gamma functions for all positive integer arguments, and for positive arguments we can also similarly find

$$B\left(n + \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}\right) = \frac{\Gamma\left(b + \frac{1}{2}\right) \cdot \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)}{\Gamma(n+1)} = \frac{(2n)!}{4^n \cdot n!} \sqrt{\pi} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{n!} = \frac{(2n)!}{4^n \cdot (n!)^2} \cdot \pi$$

And now recall the representation for the beta function as an integral with sine and cosine

$$B\left(n + \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}\right) = \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} 2 \cdot (\sin\varphi)^{2n} d\varphi = \frac{(2n)!}{4^n \cdot (n!)^2} \cdot \frac{\pi}{2}$$

We obtain a formula, the so-called Wallis integral. In a similar way we can find the integral with odd degree and in general this function is a generalization of this kind of integral.

CONCLUSION

Now to summarize, we've got

$$B(a, b) = \int_0^1 t^{a-1} \cdot (1-t)^{b-1} dt$$

$$B(a, b) = \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} 2(\sin\varphi)^{2a-1}(\cos\varphi)^{2b-1}d\varphi$$

$$B(a, b) = B(b, a)$$

$$B(a, b) = \frac{\Gamma(a) \cdot \Gamma(b)}{\Gamma(a + b)}$$

$$\Gamma(a) = \int_0^{\infty} t^{a-1} \cdot e^{-t} dt$$

$$\Gamma(a) = 2 \int_0^{\infty} 2t^{2a-1} \cdot e^{-t^2} dt$$

$$\Gamma(a + 1) = a\Gamma(a)$$

$$\Gamma(n + 1) = n!$$

$$\Gamma\left(n + \frac{1}{2}\right) = \frac{(2n)!}{4^n \cdot n!} \sqrt{\pi}.$$

Beta and gamma functions are convenient to use in order to calculate some integrals, many of which are not representable in elementary functions. Very many series and integrals encountered in analysis can be expressed through Euler beta and gamma functions. In the theory of analytic functions they appear almost on a par with elementary functions [1, 2]. Because of this, beta and gamma - functions are extensively used in mathematics and its applications, in mechanics, thermodynamics and in other branches of modern science [3,4,7,8]. In this paper, we have studied the basic properties of these functions, as well as established and analyzed the relationship between them.

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